

Machine Learning-Metaheuristic Based Optimization of Midship Plate Scantling for Very Large Crude Oil Carrier

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Abstract. This study proposes a novel optimization framework that integrates a machine learning (ML)-based prediction model with metaheuristic optimization for structural design in large tankers. The method aims to minimize the cross-sectional area of the structure while satisfying Common Structural Rules (CSR) and strength constraints. The key contribution of this study is the utilization of an ML-based prediction model to generate the initial population and its leverage in the first stage of the metaheuristic optimization process. To construct the ML-based prediction model, we generated 20,000 training datasets using existing engineering design data. Subsequently, to evaluate the effectiveness of this two-steps approach, a complex optimization problem involving over 200 design variables was addressed. The optimization results demonstrated that traditional initialization methods commonly used in metaheuristic optimization, such as randomly initialization or assigning uniform values, fail to converge to the optimal solution. In contrast, initializing the population with the ML-based prediction model enabled the optimization process to successfully converge to the optimal solution. Furthermore, it was confirmed that the convergence of the optimization process could be improved even when the ML-based model was used to generate and evaluate the initial population for extrapolated data.

Keywords: *Machine learning, Metaheuristic optimization, Structural optimization, Very large crude carrier, Common structural rules.*

1 Introduction

The shipping industry is essential to humanity and has significantly contributed to global economic growth by serving as the backbone of international trade, efficiently and cost-effectively transporting around 90% of global goods. However, it also carries a significant responsibility in addressing challenges such as marine pollution and the pressing global issues of climate change and related disasters [1], [2].

Various efforts are underway in the field of ship design and construction to optimize fuel efficiency. Optimizing the weight of ship structures has both direct and indirect effects on energy efficiency, emphasizing that optimal ship structural design serves purposes beyond merely reducing construction costs [3].

In contrast to other marine structures, merchant vessels such as tankers are governed by classification society rules, systematically developed through extensive design experience and rigorous analysis. A classification society is a non-governmental organization responsible for establishing and maintaining technical standards for constructing and operating ships and offshore structures [4]. Consequently, in practical design processes, structural member arrangements and scantlings are primarily determined through a practice-based approach that uses reference vessels to minimize design costs and enhance efficiency. Subsequently, rule-based design and finite element analysis are performed to ensure compliance with regulatory requirements and verify the overall structural strength at each stage [5].

In general, a ship has a long shape in the longitudinal direction and sufficient breadth to facilitate cargo loading. The main dimensions of a ship include its length L , breadth B , depth D , scantling draft T_S , and block coefficient C_B . Additionally, design loads consist of the global shear force, Q_{sw} and the global bending moment M_{sw} as shown in Figure 1. The main dimensions and design loads are typically determined based on the ship's purpose and operational route. During the structural design process of the ship, the arrangement and scantlings of the members are determined within a range that satisfies the required strength. Therefore, in a general sense, structural optimization involves optimizing the arrangement and scantlings of the structural members. In this study, particular attention is given to the optimization of scantling, which refers to the thickness of the Effective Plate Panel (EPP).

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Figure 1. Design structural variables of Very Large Crude Carrier (VLCC).

The history of structural optimization in ship design began in the early 1960s with the adaptation of computers [6]. By the 1960s, the classical optimization algorithms were documented and validated for assorted optimization problems. From the 1970s to the 1990s, advancements in computer performance and the widespread of personal computers facilitated the automation of calculations, leading to a diversification of optimization strategies [7], [8] presented the method with the Sequential Unconstrained Minimization Technique (SUMT) for Det Norske Veritas (DNV) rule-based design. Since the 1990s, research has tried to apply traditional optimization methods to a small number of design variables in a rule-based design approach. Nobukawa et al. introduced the procedure for the optimization based on a plastic design using SUMT for Nippon Kaiji Kyokai (NK) classification [9].

Since the 2010s, research utilizing metamodels or surrogate models has continued. In addition, studies focused on the reduction of high dimensional design space, which causes time-consuming problems, have also been ongoing. Yang demonstrated that a neuro-optimizer combining the Hopfield neural network and other simulated annealing could be used as a DNV rule-based optimization method for the midship section of the tanker [10]. The objective is to minimize the midship section area, with 13 design variables related to plate thickness and 6 design variables related to stiffeners. Na et al. proposed an optimum structural design program using the Pareto optimal based multi-objective function method [11]. This program was developed based on the CSR rule-based approach and incorporates two objective functions: minimizing the cross-sectional area and the construction cost. CSR are standardized rules that unify the rules of classification societies for tankers and bulk carriers [12]. Subsequently, Na and Karr tried to Pareto Strategy multi-objective function method considering the search direction based on Pareto optimal points, the step size, the convergence limit, and the random number generation [13]. This study considers 18 structural arrangement variables and 1 thickness variable. Shinichi et al. proposed a design space reduction method using a classification technique [14]. By applying this method, the design variables were reduced from an initial 30 plate variables and 29 stiffener variables to 6 variables each, based on principal component analysis. This study also adopted the CSR rule-based approach and used cross-sectional area minimization as an objective function. Wang et al. [15] recently introduced a general fast optimization method based on sensitivity analysis (SA) ranking, applied to a large number of design variables. Using the automated definition scheme, the oil tanker was processed to obtain 43 plating thickness variables and 53 stiffener variables, resulting in a total of 96 design variables. The fast optimization method, utilizing sensitivity ranking, was employed to minimize the sectional area. Jiang et al. [16] further proposed a method for decomposing high-dimensional problems into a series of low-dimensional sub-problems which are solved separately using Bayesian Optimization, building upon the work of Wang et al. [15].

Previous studies, as summarized in Table 1, have primarily focused on optimization methods related to rule-based design, employing a grouping technique that assigns identical scantlings to a subset of structural elements to effectively reduce the design space. However, in the case of the largest tanker designs, the midship section consists of over 400 structural members, including both plate members and stiffeners. This highlights a critical

Table 1. Summary of related works.

Study	Conventional Design Approach			Proposed Design Approach	
	Structural Scantling			Prediction	Optimization
	Design Approach	Software	Variables	Method	Method
Moe et al., 1970	DNV Rule-based	-	8	-	SUMT
Kim et al., 1983	KR Rule-based	-	10	-	SUMT
Nobukawa et al., 1990	NK Rule-based	-	14	-	SUMT+Taylor Exp.
Yang et al., 1996	DNV Rule-based	-	19	-	Neuro-Optimizer
Na et al., 2008	CSR Rule-based	SeaTrust	5	-	Pareto-Optimal
Shinichi et al., 2014	CSR Rule-based	PrimeShip	12	-	PCA-GA
Na., 2016	CSR Rule-based	SeaTrust	20	-	Pareto-Search
Wang., 2023	CSR Rule-based	Mars2000	96	-	SA
Jiang., 2024	CSR Rule-based	Mars2000	96	-	Cooperative BO
This study	Practice-based	-	Abt.200	MLP	-
	CSR Rule-based	In-house	Abt.200	-	TLBO

need to the development of optimization techniques applicable to large-scale tanker designs. In addition, the evaluation of the strength requires a significant amount of computational time and is an essential step for strength verification and approval. Therefore, an alternative approach, rather than solely reducing the complexity of the optimization problem, is necessary.

In the field of structural optimization for ship design, significant progress has been made in rule-based design and finite element analysis. However, two major limitations still persist. First, there is a lack of research addressing high-dimensional problems associated with the extensive design variables of very large ships. Most recent studies have focused on relatively smaller tankers, employing grouping techniques to unify the dimensions of adjacent structural members, thus heuristically transitioning the problem into a low-dimensional one [17]. Second, optimization methodologies face challenges when applied to real-world ship design. Actual ship design requires the integration of engineering weights in an organic manner to identify optimal solutions. However, prior studies are often limited to specific scenarios or lack broad applicability in practical design contexts.

Recent progress in data-driven methodologies presents compelling solutions to this challenge. In particular, various machine learning (ML) and deep learning techniques have demonstrated the ability to surpass traditional numerical methods based on physics and mechanics [18]-[22]. Additionally, data-driven strategies leveraging experimental data have been successfully applied across numerous engineering fields, efficiently solving various design and optimization problems [23]-[26].

The structural design optimization of very large tankers with numerous design variables presents significant challenges, often impeding the derivation of optimal solutions and convergence during the optimization process. In optimization problems with many design variables, even with sufficiently large population size and numerous iterations to promote convergence, the solution may still fail to reach the optimal result.

In this study, we propose an ML-based prediction model for metaheuristic optimization in the structural design of large tankers. The ML-based prediction model was utilized to initialize the initial population in the first stage of metaheuristic optimization, aiming to improve optimization convergence. To train the ML-based prediction model, we employed existing engineering design data comprising decades of accumulated ship design records. The ML-based prediction model consists of three sub-models, each designed to evaluate the initial population corresponding to specific design variable values. The appropriateness of the initial population is assessed based on the evaluation results of these sub-models. In this study, the three sub-models were constructed using the Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) model, which has been commonly used to effectively model complex patterns and data, demonstrating excellent performance for various engineering problems. Furthermore, we adopted the teaching-learning-based optimization (TLBO) algorithms for metaheuristic optimization [27].

The main contributions of our research are as follows: 1) the proposal of a high-dimensional optimization approach capable of handling more than 200 design variables, reflecting real-world design scenarios 2) the construction of an ML-based prediction model to generate the initial population and its utilization in the metaheuristic optimization process. This study aims to develop two-steps metaheuristic optimization framework that enhances optimization convergence and reduces the time required to derive optimal solutions by leveraging an initialized population through an ML-based prediction model.

Figure 2. Holistic Workflow of proposal two steps optimization framework.

2 Proposed two-steps optimization framework

We present two-steps optimization framework that integrates an ML-based prediction process and the metaheuristic optimization for CSR rule requirements as shown in Figure 2. The detailed input and output variables for each model are listed in Table 2. The overall procedure can be summarized as following steps:

- Step 1. Determination of principal particulars
- Step 2. Determination of EPP data
- Step 3. Prediction of pressure and normal stress
- Step 4. Calculation of rule-required thickness
- Step 5. Determination of Initial thickness
- Step 6. Initialization of population from the initial thickness
- Step 7. Optimization using TLBO
- Step 8. Termination of the optimization process

First, the principal particulars, including the main dimensions and global loads, are determined during the contract phase. In the second step, the arrangement of plate and stiffener members is performed to generate the EPP information, which forms the basic unit of the plate structure. In the third step, the trained sub-models, MLP1 and MLP2, are used to predict the local pressure and stress acting on each EPP, respectively. In the fourth step, the predicted local pressure and normal stress are employed to calculate the minimum required thickness as specified by the CSR. The minimum required thickness is calculated using the reconstructed formula:

$$t_{req} = 0.0158 \alpha_p b \sqrt{\frac{|P_{1,st} + P_{1,dy} + P_{2,st} + P_{2,dy}|}{\chi \left(\beta - \alpha \frac{|\sigma_x|}{R_{eH}} \right) R_{eH}}} \quad (1)$$

where α_p , b are correction factors for the panel aspect ratio, and breadth of the plate panel, respectively. P is the design local pressure for the considered design load set. In this study, The local pressure consists of four components: major static, $P_{1,st}$, major dynamic, $P_{1,dy}$, adjacent static, $P_{2,st}$, and adjacent dynamic, $P_{2,dy}$. The

Table 2. Input and output variables for each model.

Model	Input variable													Output variable			
MLP1	L	B	D	T_S	-	-	-	x_i	y_i	z_i	-	-	-	G_i	LC_l	-	$P_{1,st}, P_{1,dy}, P_{2,st}, P_{2,dy}$
MLP2	L	B	D	T_S	-	-	-	x_i	y_i	z_i	-	-	-	G_i	LC_l	-	σ_x
MLP3	L	B	D	-	-	M_{sw}	-	y_i	-	a_i	-	-	G_i	-	$t_{i,req}$	-	$t_{i,init}$
TLBO	L	B	D	T_S	C_B	M_{sw}	Q_{sw}	x	y	z	a	b	k	G	LC	t_{init}	t_{opt}

permissible bending stress coefficient for the plate was calculated using the hull girder bending stress, σ_x and specified minimum yield stress of steel, R_{eH} .

In the fifth step, the calculated minimum required thickness is used as input to estimate the initial design variables using the MLP3 model. Starting from the sixth step, the metaheuristic optimization process is initiated. The initial population is clustered into groups for initialization. In the seventh step, the generated initial variable clusters are optimized through the teaching and learning phases to explore the optimal solution. Finally, the framework terminates after performing updates for the specified number of iterations, resulting in the optimal solution.

3 Prediction model for initial design variables

3.1 Data collection

The dataset used for constructing MLP models was extracted from the midship sections of six vessels, comprising calculation information for over 200 EPPs. These data account for all CSR load combinations for each EPP and were preprocessed by removing outliers through a heuristic approach. A total of 20,000 datasets were generated by collecting data from 6 vessels constructed within the past decade.

3.2 ML-based prediction model

In population-based optimization algorithms, it is important to set an appropriate initial population, as it significantly influences the convergence and performance of the optimization process [28], [29] and [30]. A well-trained prediction model, such as an ML model, facilitates real-time evaluations, whereas traditional engineering approaches often require several days to complete the same task. In this study, the MLP models were utilized to generate the initial population for the metaheuristic optimization.

To configure the initial population for metaheuristic optimization, an MLP1 model was developed to predict the local pressure of the EPP. The local pressure prediction consists of four components: $P_{1,st}$, $P_{1,dy}$, $P_{2,st}$, and $P_{2,dy}$. Additionally, an MLP2 model was constructed to estimate σ_x of the hull girder, as summarized in Table 2. Subsequently, the required plate thickness was calculated using Equation (1), based on the local pressure and normal stress values predicted by the MLP1 and MLP2 models. Finally, the calculated required thickness and the input conditions were used as input data for an MLP3 model, which predicted the initial plate thickness to configure the initial population for metaheuristic optimization. In summary, the initial population was configured through the following steps:

- Step 1. Develop MLP1 and MLP2 models to predict local pressure and normal stress values.
- Step 2. Calculate the required plate thickness using Equation (1).
- Step 3. Predict the initial plate thickness using the MLP3 model, based on the calculated plate thickness.

To achieve optimal model performance with the given datasets, the Bayesian Optimization and Hyperband (BOHB) algorithm [31] was employed. This method automatically searches for the best hyperparameters within a predefined range. The hyperparameter search ranges for the BOHB algorithm are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Hyperparameter of BOHB.

Hyperparameter	Search Range
Neurons	2^2 to 2^8
Learning rate	$1e^{-5}$ to $1e^{-3}$
Layers	1 to 10
Batch size	2^3 to 2^6
Epoch	50 to 5000

During training, input data were normalized to a range of 0 to 1, while output data were scaled to 0 to 0.9. The MLP models were trained using the Mean Squared Error (MSE) loss function. The dataset was split into 80% for training and 20% for testing. To mitigate overfitting during the construction of the MLP models, 5-fold cross-validation was employed.

All MLP models were developed using a system with an Intel i9-12900KF processor, 128 GB of RAM, and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3050 GPU. To evaluate the performance of the MLP models, the accuracy of the predicted value was determined by comparing them with the corresponding value of test data as follows:

$$P_{acc} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(100 - \frac{|\bar{P}_i - P_i|}{|P_i|} \times 100 \right) \quad (2)$$

where P_{acc} represents the relative accuracy of the MLP models, n denotes the number of test data, P_i is the ground truth data of the i -th test data, and \bar{P}_i is the corresponding model output.

Figure 3 (a)-(f) illustrates the prediction results for the EPP local pressure of four components, hull girder normal stress, and initial plate thickness. The trained MLP models showed high accuracy: approximately $99.15 \pm 2.57\%$ for static pressure, $97.79 \pm 10.1\%$ for dynamic pressure, $98.87 \pm 3.6\%$ for normal stress, and $97.53 \pm 3.92\%$ for the final initial plate thickness.

Figure 3. The performance of MLP models, (a) Results of the major static pressure, (b) Results of the major dynamic pressure, (c) Results of the adjacent static pressure, (d) Results of the adjacent dynamic pressure, (e) Results of the normal stress, (f) Results of the thickness

4 Midship section optimization problem

The objective function of the optimization is to minimize the cross-sectional area while satisfying four strength requirement constraints. Among these, Constraint 1, which calculates the required thickness for each plate element, was utilized as the lower boundary during the population initialization phase of the TLBO algorithm. This utilization effectively enhances the optimization process by reducing the search space within the large design space, thereby improving computational efficiency in the initial stage.

The following Figure 4 presents a three-dimensional visualization diagram that illustrates the overall flow of the TLBO algorithm from the perspective of each data dimension. In this visualization, each cubic represents a variable generated during a single optimization process, providing an intuitive understanding of the algorithm's operation across multiple dimensions.

Engineering is a process of deriving the best solution based on the given conditions, making it unsuitable to refer to it as a global optimum. Therefore, the global optimum sought in this study will be described as a reference optimal value or region based on recently designed ships.

4.1 Optimization problem definition

In this study, the optimization problem can be stated as follows:

$$\text{To find } \mathbf{T} = \begin{Bmatrix} t_1 \\ t_2 \\ \vdots \\ t_{n-1} \\ t_n \end{Bmatrix} \text{ which minimize } f(\mathbf{T}) \quad (3)$$

where, \mathbf{T} is an n -dimensional design variables vector, n is the number of variables,

Objective function:

$$\text{Min. } f(\mathbf{T}) = \sum_{i=1}^n (b_i \times t_i) + \sum_{k=1}^c (w_k \times P_k) \quad (4)$$

where c is the number of constraints, b_i and t_i are the breadth and the thickness of EPP_i , respectively. w_k is engineering factor, P_k is the summation of the penalty for k -th constraint function. The objective function consists of two components: a section area calculation part and a penalty term for constraints.

Subject to:

$$g_1(\mathbf{T}) = t_i - t_{i,req} \geq 0 \quad (5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} g_2(\mathbf{T}) &= Z_{btm} - Z_{k,btm,req} \geq 0 \text{ at bottom} \\ &= Z_{dk} - Z_{k,dk,req} \geq 0 \text{ at deck} \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$g_3(\mathbf{T}) = Q_{cap} - Q_k \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

$$g_4(\mathbf{T}) = \eta_{i,all} - \eta_i \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

where $g_j(\mathbf{T})$ represents the respective constraints, including plate yielding strength, hull girder bending strength, hull girder shear strength, and plate buckling strength. t_i and $t_{i,req}$ are input plate thickness and required plate thickness of EPP_i . Z_{btm} and Z_{dk} are section modulus calculated from input \mathbf{T} at the bottom and deck region. $Z_{k,btm,req}$ and $Z_{k,dk,req}$ are section modulus requirement for k -th design load combination. Q_{cap} and Q_k are the hull girder shear capacity and shear force for k -th design load combination. η_i and $\eta_{i,all}$ are maximum plate utilization factor and allowable buckling utilization factor of EPP_i .

Figure 4. The schematic diagram for TLBO algorithm

When:

$$P_1 = \sum_{i=1}^n p_1(\mathbf{T}), \quad p_1(\mathbf{T}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } g_1(\mathbf{T}) \geq 0 \\ t_{i,req}/t_i & \text{if } g_1(\mathbf{T}) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

$$P_2 = \sum_{k=1}^4 p_{2,dk}(\mathbf{T}) + p_{2,btm}(\mathbf{T}), \quad p_2(\mathbf{T}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } g_2(\mathbf{T}) \geq 0 \\ Z_{k,req}/Z & \text{if } g_2(\mathbf{T}) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$P_3 = \sum_{k=1}^4 p_3(\mathbf{T}), \quad p_3(\mathbf{T}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } g_3(\mathbf{T}) \geq 0 \\ Q_k/Q_{cap} & \text{if } g_3(\mathbf{T}) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

$$P_4 = \sum_{i=1}^n p_4(\mathbf{T}), \quad p_4(\mathbf{T}) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } g_4(\mathbf{T}) \leq 0 \\ \eta_i/\eta_{i,all} & \text{if } g_4(\mathbf{T}) > 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $p_j(\mathbf{T})$ represents the respective penalties, including plate yielding strength, hull girder bending strength, hull girder shear strength, and plate buckling strength.

4.2 Load combination

The design local pressure for the considered design load set is calculated at the load calculation point of the EPP within the structural region, as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Design load sets (CSR, IACS, 2024)

Structural Region	Design load set	Load component	Design load	Loading condition
External shell and Upper deck	SEA-1	P_{ex}	S+D	Full load condition
	SEA-2	P_{ex}	S	Harbour condition
Water ballast Tank	WB-1	$P_{in} - P_{ex}$	S+D	Normal ballast condition
	WB-2	$P_{in} - P_{ex}$	S+D	Water ballast exchange
	WB-3	$P_{in} - P_{ex}$	S	Harbour condition
Cargo oil tank	OT-1	P_{in}	S+D	Full load condition
	OT-2	P_{in}	S+D	Partial load condition
	OT-3	P_{in}	S	Harbour condition

The load components are categorized into internal pressure, acting on the internal side, and external pressure, acting on the opposite side. The respective pressures are applied to each structural region and design load case, including static (S) and combined static and dynamic (S+D) loads.

Based on the dynamic load case, 11 conditions of the Equivalent Design Wave (EDW) as defined in the CSR, two conditions of vertical wave bending moment (hogging and sagging), two conditions of still water bending moment (hogging and sagging), and eight design load sets for specific structural regions are combined. These combinations, as summarized in Table 5, result in a total of 352 load cases

Table 5. Design load scenarios (CSR, IACS, 2024)

Design load scenario		Harbour condition	Seagoing condition	Ballast condition	
Load components		Static	Static +Dynamic	Static +Dynamic	
Hull girder	Vertical Bending Moment	M_{sw}	$M_{sw} + M_{wv}$	$M_{sw} + M_{wv}$	
	Horizontal Bending Moment	-	M_{wh}	M_{wh}	
	Vertical Shear Force	Q_{sw}	$Q_{sw} + Q_{wv}$	$Q_{sw} + Q_{wv}$	
	Torsional Moment	-	M_{wt}	M_{wt}	
Local	P_{ex}	Upper deck	-	P_D	-
		Shell Plate	P_S	$P_S + P_D$	$P_S + P_D$
	P_{in}	Ballast tanks	$Max(P_S, P_D)$	$P_S + P_D$	$P_S + P_D$
		Cargo Holds	P_D	$P_S + P_D$	-

4.3 Four constraints

The mission of the structural designer is to design a structure that can withstand the operational and environmental requirements designated throughout its lifetime. In the allowable stress design, the focus is on keeping the stress from the design loads under a certain working stress level. The criterion of the allowable stress design is typically given by:

$$\sigma_{act} < \sigma_{all} \quad (13)$$

where σ_{act} is working stress and σ_{all} is allowable stress.

In contrast to allowable stress design, limit state design explicitly considers the various conditions under which a structure may fail to fulfill its intended function. For these conditions, the applicable capacity or strength is estimated and used as a limit during the design process to account for such behavior. In this research, the optimization problem has 4 constraints:

- Constraint 1. Plate yielding strength
- Constraint 2. Hull girder bending strength
- Constraint 3. Hull girder shear strength
- Constraint 4. Plate buckling strength

The first constraint represents the plate yielding based on a uniformly loaded plate in a continuous field, with stiffening along the long edges, a and frames supporting the stiffeners along the short edges, b according to the theory of the plate elastic deflection [32]. The thickness of EPP is required to be taken bigger than:

$$t_{req} = 0.0158 \alpha_p b \sqrt{\frac{|P|}{\chi C_a R_{eH}}} \quad (14)$$

where C_a represents the permissible bending stress coefficient for the plate, R_{eH} represents specified minimum yield stress, α_p , b are respectively correction factors for the panel aspect ratio, and breadth of plate panel, P is the design local pressure for the considered design load set.

The permissible bending stress coefficient is calculated using the hull girder bending stress and specified minimum yield stress and defined as follows

$$C_a = \beta - \alpha \frac{|\sigma_{hg}|}{R_{eH}} \quad (15)$$

where α represents the coefficient for the stiffened plating system, β represents the coefficient for the load case. The correction factor, α_p for the plate panel aspect ratio is calculated by the length, a and breadth, b of plate panel.

The second constraint corresponds to the hull girder bending stress, which is related to the normal stress acting on the EPPs. The normal stress induced by vertical bending moments is evaluated for both hogging and sagging conditions. Here, f_β represents the seagoing condition factor 1.05, M_{wv} denotes the vertical wave bending moment in a seagoing condition considered 352 load combinations, Z_B and Z_D refer to the net section modulus at the bottom and deck position, respectively, as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Required section modulus (CSR, IACS, 2024)

Operation	$Z_{btm,req}$ At bottom,		$Z_{dk,req}$ at deck	
	Hogging	Sagging	Hogging	Sagging
Seagoing (S+D)	$\frac{M_{sw_sea_hog} + f_\beta M_{wv}}{\sigma_{btm,perm}}$	$\frac{M_{sw_sea_sag} + f_\beta M_{wv}}{\sigma_{btm,perm}}$	$\frac{M_{sw_sea_hog} + f_\beta M_{wv}}{\sigma_{dk,perm}}$	$\frac{M_{sw_sea_sag} + f_\beta M_{wv}}{\sigma_{dk,perm}}$
Harbour (S)	$\frac{M_{sw_harb_hog}}{\sigma_{btm,perm}}$	$\frac{M_{sw_sea_hog}}{\sigma_{btm,perm}}$	$\frac{M_{sw_harb_hog}}{\sigma_{dk,perm}}$	$\frac{M_{sw_harb_hog}}{\sigma_{dk,perm}}$

The third constraint relates to the hull girder shear strength, which represents the ship's capacity to resist shear forces. The shear strength is evaluated by calculating the shear flow of all EPPs. The total vertical hull girder shear capacity, Q_{cap} is the hull girder shear capacity for all EPPs contributing to the hull girder shear of the considered transverse section and defined as follows:

$$Q_{cap} = \min_i \left(\frac{\tau_{i,perm} t_i}{q_{v,i}} 10^{-3} \right) \quad (16)$$

where t_i is the net thickness of EPP_i , $q_{v,i}$ is contribution ratio for hull girder shear force per unit length for EPP_i , $\tau_{i,perm}$ is permissible shear stress decided by material factor.

Table 7. Vertical shear force (CSR, IACS, 2024)

Operation	Q_{oper}	
	Hogging	Sagging
Seagoing (S+D)	$ Q_{sw_sea_hog} + f_{\beta} Q_{wv} $	$ Q_{sw_sea_sag} + f_{\beta} Q_{wv} $
Harbour (S)	$ Q_{sw_harb_hog} $	$ Q_{sw_harb_sag} $

The shear capacity must not exceed the permissible value determined in Table 7. The final constraint represents the buckling strength of the EPP under in-plane compression, shear, or lateral loads. This capacity provides a conservative estimate of the ultimate strength by accounting for the elastic post-buckling behavior of plates [33], [34]. Permitting elastic buckling in slender stiffened panels allows for significant elastic deflections and reduced in-plane stiffness at high utilization levels, while still maintaining structural integrity. It is expressed as follows:

$$\eta_{act} \leq \eta_{all} \quad (17)$$

For the combined loads, the utilization factor, η_{act} is defined as the ratio of the equivalent applied stress and the corresponding buckling capacity. η_{all} is allowable buckling utilization factor, 1.0 for load case (S+D), 0.8 for load case (S) as proposed in the CSR.

4.4 Constraint matrix

The constraint matrix is constructed to perform rapid calculations for the four strength requirements. A detailed examination of the constraints is presented in Figure 5, demonstrating the calculation process.

Figure 5. The schematic diagram for No.1 Constraint, $g_1(T)$.

First, based on the initial inputs of principal particulars and EPP data, the section properties are calculated by incorporating the thickness information of n EPPs. These section properties are computed beforehand, as they directly influence the stress calculations acting on the EPP. The transparent section in the center of the diagram illustrates the process of calculating 352 load combinations. For each load combination, 110 backup variables are computed, followed by the calculation of local pressure and normal stress values. This process is represented as a single metric in the Rule Requirement Constraint Matrix. Finally, the maximum required thickness among the 352 load combinations is determined as the output. Similarly, constraint matrices are constructed for the remaining three constraints, each designed to fit the strength calculation process required for the respective condition.

5 Results and discussion

5.1 Optimization results

In this study, three cases for configuring the initial population, consisting of 206 design variables, in metaheuristic optimization were tested to evaluate the performance of the proposed two-steps optimization process: (1) a random initial population, (2) a uniform initial population, and (3) an MLP3 model-based initial population. Figure 6 illustrates the convergence history curves of the EPP plate optimization for three cases. Specifically, Figure 6(a) represents the scenario where the initial plate thickness was randomly initialized within the range of 10 mm to 30 mm. Figure 6(b) shows the case where it was empirically set to 15 mm, based on the thickness required in the design process. Lastly, Figure 6(c) depicts the configuration using the MLP3 model for determining the initial plate thickness. Based on the optimization results, it is evident that randomly initialized values or assigning uniform values fail to converge to the optimal plate thickness range, as indicated by the gray lines in Figure 6(a)-(b). In contrast, when the initial plate thickness is determined using the MLP3 model, convergence to the optimal plate thickness is achieved in approximately 20 iterations.

Furthermore, when the initial population was initialized using the MLP3 model, all cases with population sizes ranging from 500 to 3000 converged to the optimal region. On the other hand, significant deviations were observed depending on the population size when the initial population was set randomly. A similar trend was observed when the initial population was configured with uniform values.

Figure 6(d) illustrates the convergence times for a population size P of 1000 across three different cases. In the cases of random-based and uniform-based initial populations, convergence to a local optimum region takes over 7 h. In contrast, the MLP3 model-based initial population achieves convergence to the reference optimum in just 2 h 30 min. These results suggest that using the MLP3 model to construct the initial population for metaheuristic optimization can significantly reduce the time needed to derive optimal solutions compared to traditional engineering approaches, which usually take several days to complete.

Figure 6. Optimization results of three cases, (a) randomly initialization, (b) uniformly initialization, (c) MLP model-based initialization, (d) Comparison.

5.2 Application optimization problem

A new vessel was designed earlier this year to meet high specifications, incorporating eco-friendly features and premium earning potential. These were achieved through improved fuel efficiency, reduced emissions, and increased carrying capacity.

The vessel used in the case study has a length of 319.1 m, a breadth of 60.0 m, a depth of 30.6 m, a scantling draft of 22.9 m, and a block coefficient of 0.8. This vessel lies outside the design variable space covered by the training dataset, exhibiting specifications that differ significantly from those of the vessels used to construct the MLP models. Due to the increased height, the number of EPPs is slightly higher than that of the original vessel, total 216 EPPs, as summarized in Table 8. Consequently, we evaluated the performance of the proposed two-steps optimization process to verify its effectiveness for extrapolated data.

Table 8. Definition of design variables

Design Variables	Structural Group
$t_1 \sim t_{31}$	Bottom Shell
$t_{32} \sim t_{34}$	Bilge
$t_{35} \sim t_{66}$	Side Shell
$t_{67} \sim t_{100}$	Upper Deck
$t_{101} \sim t_{125}$	Inner Bottom
$t_{126} \sim t_{134}$	Hopper Side
$t_{135} \sim t_{159}$	Longitudinal Bulkhead
$t_{160} \sim t_{192}$	Inner Hull
$t_{193} \sim t_{201}$	Bottom Girder
$t_{202} \sim t_{206}$	Horizontal Stringer
$t_{207} \sim t_{216}$	Side Stringer

The accuracy of the MLP3 model in predicting the initial plate thickness was relatively low, at approximately 91%, compared to the 97% accuracy achieved for the vessel dataset. However, the 216 design variables appear to have converged to the reference optimum as illustrated in Figure 7. Based on these results, despite the reduced accuracy of the MLP3 model due to extrapolated data, this highlights the importance of generating a well-designed initial population in metaheuristic optimization.

Figure 7. Result of application optimization problem.

The basic structural design of the ship required approximately one week: three days for entering preliminary information into the classification program, two days for verifying calculations, and two days for the dimension

optimization process. In contrast, applying the method proposed in this study allowed the final dimensions to be determined in just 3 to 4 hours.

The study on the application optimization problem demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed two-steps optimization process in reducing the search space, validating its role in enhancing optimization convergence. Even when the case study vessel deviated from the training data, the proposed framework effectively narrowed the search range, enabling effectively convergence toward the reference optimum.

6 Conclusions

This study proposes a novel two-steps optimization framework that combines metaheuristic optimization and an ML-based prediction model to address challenges in ship structural design. By employing the MLP model to generate the initial population and integrating it with the TLBO algorithm, the proposed method achieves improved scalability and computational efficiency. The results demonstrate the potential of this approach in optimizing complex ship structures with over 200 design variables, representing a substantial improvement over traditional rule-based methods with limited scope and flexibility.

A major contribution of this research is the development of MLP models trained on a large dataset comprising approximately 25,000 ship design instances. These models achieved prediction accuracies exceeding 97%, thereby significantly enhancing the estimation of initial plate thicknesses. By providing superior initial values, the optimization process demonstrates faster convergence, even within extensive design spaces, as evidenced by the rapid convergence achieved using relatively small population sizes in the TLBO algorithm.

A comparative analysis of various initialization strategies revealed that traditional methods, which rely on random or uniform initialization, often lead to suboptimal solutions or slower convergence rates. Conversely, integrating MLP predictions consistently facilitated convergence toward the reference optimum, highlighting the critical role of data-driven starting points in optimization.

Furthermore, the application optimization study conducted on a newly designed vessel confirmed the robustness of the proposed method. Despite significant differences in hull form and specifications compared to the training dataset, the framework successfully optimized the design within hours, showcasing its adaptability to novel design scenarios. This result underscores the ability of the proposed two-steps optimization process to handle extrapolated data in the design space, which is a crucial feature for real-world applications.

However, certain limitations must be acknowledged. While this study focused on optimizing the midship section, extending the framework to other ship sections or comprehensive design processes may present additional challenges. Moreover, the performance of the MLP models relies heavily on the quality and diversity of the training data; enhancing dataset coverage could further improve model accuracy, particularly for non-standard designs.

This research bridges the gap between traditional rule-based methods and modern optimization techniques by integrating an ML-based prediction model with metaheuristic optimization. The findings lay the foundation for future research that could leverage advanced algorithms, such as hybrid optimization approaches [35], [36], to further enhance design efficiency. In conclusion, this study provides a solid foundation for advancing ship structural optimization by integrating predictive analytics with advanced optimization techniques. It also highlights the potential to align ship design more closely with sustainability goals by incorporating environmental factors, such as life-cycle emissions, into the optimization objectives. Future research focusing on holistic optimization, environmental objectives, and real-world adaptability could further enhance the impact of this approach, paving the way for sustainable and efficient ship designs.

Acknowledgments

This work is supported by HD Hyundai Heavy Industry Industry-Academia Research Project.

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